

Quantum Mechanics and Complex Numbers Part III

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In Part II of this note, we argued that if one describes a bound particle in a potential in a statistical manner, like classical statistical mechanics, one is led to a complex, periodic space invariant probability, $\exp(ipx)$, for a free particle. We showed that $\exp(ipx)$ represents a two vector solution to the vector operated on by a rotation matrix (using $\cos(px)$, $-\sin(px)$) set equal to a translation operator $1 + \delta X d/dx$ operating on the same vector.

In this note, we examine the electromagnetic scenario. The idea of a “wave” describing a photon first emerged with Maxwell and his equations in the 1800s, with interference/diffraction and the speed of light both appearing. It was later found (Einstein and the photoelectric effect) that electromagnetic energy is not spread out all over space like a wave, but is concentrated. Furthermore, if one uses probabilistic ideas to obtain $\exp(ipx)$ for a quantum particle, like an electron, which undergoes two slit interference, then why would not two slit interference for photons also be considered in terms of probability? In this note, we examine these ideas.

Quantum Particle

In Part II, we considered the problem of a stochastic potential giving rise to free particle probabilities. In classical physics, interparticle collisions establish stochastic equilibrium based on temperature so one has $f(p)$ as a probability. In the presence of a potential there is varying density, and so a separable solution $f(p)g(x) = \exp(-pp/2mT) \exp(-V(x)/T)$. In the quantum case, one does not have this separability, but we argued there should be periodicity and invariance in space. This invariance may be given by:

$$\begin{vmatrix} \cos(px) & -\sin(px) \\ \sin(px) & \cos(px) \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} |a(px)\rangle \\ |b(px)\rangle \end{vmatrix} = \exp(dX d/dx) \begin{vmatrix} |a(px)\rangle \\ |b(px)\rangle \end{vmatrix} \quad ((1))$$

Setting pdX small yields $\cos(px)=1$ to first order, $\sin(px)=pdx$ to first order and $\exp(dX d/dx) = 1 + dX d/dx$. A solution for $a(px)$ is $\cos(px)$ and for $b(px)$ $\sin(px)$ leading to $\exp(ipx)$.

Here we wish to focus on a tiny translation to the right followed by one to the left. In such a case:

$R(-px)R(px) = 1$ so the first order expansion term in pdX should disappear and there should be at best $(pdX)(pdX)$ order terms.

$$\begin{vmatrix} 1 & pdX \\ -pdX & 1 \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} |1\rangle \\ |0\rangle \end{vmatrix} = \begin{vmatrix} 1 & 0 \\ 0 & 1 \end{vmatrix} \begin{vmatrix} |1\rangle \\ |0\rangle \end{vmatrix} \quad \text{and} \quad (1 - p dX d/dx) (1 + pdX d/dx) = 1 - pp dX dX d/dx d/dx$$

((2))

One may note that $-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$ is, up to a factor of $1/2m$ (and dropping $\frac{d}{dx}$), the kinetic energy operator in the Schrodinger equation.

Thus, if one sees $-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$ in a scalar equation, there is a mathematical scenario equivalent to a forward rotation multiplied by a backward $R(-px)R(px)$ set equal to a forward translation multiplied by a backward one. As a mathematical option, this does not necessarily represent physics, but it can. Thus, one need not think of $-\frac{d}{dx} \frac{d}{dx}$ acting on a scalar function. It may act on a two vector with the idea of spatial invariance present i.e. a translation is the same as a mathematical rotation with $\cos(pdX)$ etc used. We wish to apply this idea to the wave equation.

Wave Equation

The wave equation appears for physical waves in a medium such as sound or waves on a string etc. It is given by:

$$\frac{d^2}{dt^2} W(x,t) - 1/v^2 \frac{d^2}{dx^2} W(x,t) = 0 \quad ((3)) \quad \text{where } v \text{ is velocity}$$

A separable solution is available $\cos(\omega t)\cos(kx)$ or $\sin(\omega t)\sin(kx)$ and a linear combination is equivalent to $\cos(-\omega t+kx)$. Real values are used because the waves are real. Furthermore, with the separable solution one considers a continual stream i.e. a standing wave type scenario because at a given x the solution in time is periodic.

Electromagnetism

Maxwell found that if sources (charge and current) were set to zero in his electromagnetic equations, he could obtain wave equations for both E (electric field) and B (magnetic field). At first, these were considered to be physical waves with energy spread over space. These waves described two slit interference and diffraction experiments and used real values i.e. for linear polarized light a photon moves in the z direction with say $E_x = E_0 \cos(k(t-z))$ (x direction) + $B_y \cos(k(t-z))$ (y direction). For the photon, $E_0 = B_0$ and $ck = \omega$ (we take $c=1$). Given that these solutions hold for electric and magnetic fields, one may link k and ω to energy density and momentum flow i.e. $\frac{1}{2} E \cdot E + \frac{1}{2} B \cdot B$ ($c=1$) and $1/\mu_0 E \times B$. It turns out that the energy of the photon is $\hbar \omega$ and momentum $\hbar k$ i.e. energy and momentum are related to frequency and wavelength.

If one considers a photon as an object traveling in a certain direction, the idea of its energy being spread out over space may be problematic. A wave function has a separable solution so one may go to a point x and observe a periodic t function. In general, $E(x,t)$ for Maxwell's equations with sources does not have this property.

In this note, we argue that because one may write a wave equation for E and B which are directly related to the energy density and momentum of a moving particle (with concentrated energy), one has invariance in space coupled with periodicity. E and B are real, so a real solution is taken i.e. they both behave as $\cos(k(t-x))$ for linearly polarized light.

We have shown above that mathematically, $\exp(ipx)$ is a solution of a rotation equation set equal to a translation. Periodicity is present in the frequency of the rotation angle i.e. $\cos(px)$ see ((2)). For a wave equation, one does not have a translation, but rather $-d/dx$ multiplied by $1/v$ where v is the velocity. We have argued above that this is equivalent to a two dimensional vector i.e. $\exp(ipx)$ operated on by $R(-pdX)R(pdX)$ or by a translation to the right followed by one to the left. Thus, a scalar equation may have matrix solutions just as Dirac was able to take the scalar Klein-Gordon equation and write an equation linear in p and E ($-id/dx$ and id/dt). There must, however, be a physical reason for doing this. In the Dirac case, the experimentally observed spin gave justification. For the electromagnetic case, we argue that the absence of a physical wave with energy spread out over space gives justification for spatial invariant, two dimensional periodic probability as being a main idea.

The Idea of Probability

We argue that the wave equations of electromagnetism, even though they represent physical observables E (electric field) and B (magnetic) field, establish a probabilistic picture of a periodic two dimensional mathematical rotation in px occurring in a photon as it translates with momentum p . This same behaviour holds for a quantum object such as an electron. In both cases, one considers $\exp(ipx)$ related to probability, so one does not follow a photon or particle in time and space as in classical physics even though it travels in time and space in an experiment. The probabilistic picture yields the results of interactions which occur with photons or particles based on the wavelength $1/p$. If one wishes to make px Lorentz invariant for a free particle, one may use $\exp(-iEt+ipx)$.

It is interesting to note that for both a quantum particle (electron etc) and a photon, there is a link to the classical action. For a quantum particle moving at constant speed v , the relativistic or non-relativistic actions $-T \text{ mo } \sqrt{1-vv}$ or $T.5\text{movv}$ with $v=X/T$ may be varied with respect to X and T yielding: d/dt Action = $-E$ and d/dx Action = p . One may form $\exp(-iEt+px)$ separating X and T (which are usually not separated if one has constant velocity). $-Et+px$ is also equivalent to: $L = -H + v dL/dv$ integrated over dt where $dL/dv=p$. For a classical particle $-HT$ yields ET and vpT is equivalent to xp . For a photon, $L = -H + vdL/dv$ yields $-ET + cpT$ and c may be written as X/T yielding $-Et+px$. Thus, one may write $\exp(-iEt+px)$ for both cases.

For a two slit experiment, one may consider $\exp(ipx)$ values as a probability and add these factors for different paths. For example, one scenario is to have a particle move from one slit to a point on a screen. Another scenario is to have the particle move from the second slit to the same point. Other scenarios involve the particle weaving through one slit to the other before moving to the screen etc. (1) One does not follow the particle in space and time and so these represent a probability picture.

Finally, it may be noted that in the literature it is argued (2), that a quantum photon wavefunction is $E + iB$. This wavefunction satisfies an equation similar to the Dirac one, but for a spin 1 particle i.e.

$$id/dt (E+iB)_j = i e_l(jk) (-id/dx_l (E + iB)_k \text{ where } e_{ijk} \text{ is the Levi-Civita symbol } ((4))$$

This follows directly from Maxwell's equations with no sources, but focuses on spin related to rotating E and B fields in the case of polarized photons. We argue in this note, that one does not need to consider spin in order to identify the basic idea of a two-dimensional periodic-space invariant probability for a free particle. $\exp(ipx)$ should emerge from the wave equation derived from Maxwell's equations as we have argued. $-d/dx$ in the wave equation is linked to $R(-px)R(px)$ OR a forward translation followed by a backwards one. Similarly, as in the Dirac case, a spin differential equation may be obtained which is also consistent with the wave equation. (In the Dirac case, one has the Klein-Gordon equation.). Thus, we argue that a wave equation with scalars may need to be analyzed in more detail because it may give rise to mathematical solutions using matrices which may be linked to physical reality.

Conclusion

In conclusion, we consider the electromagnetic wave solutions for E (electric field) and B (magnetic field) which follow from Maxwell's equations. Originally, these were thought to represent waves with energy spread throughout space. In this note, we argue that even though the equations are related to physical observables (E, B) which are real, one may consider the periodicity of the solution to be linked to spatial invariance i.e. $-d/dx$ is equivalent to $R(-pdX)R(pdX)$ (i.e. a forward rotation followed by a backward one) and also to a $(1-dX/dx)$ forward translation followed by a backwards one. Both of these operate on a 2-vector i.e. $\exp(ipx)$. In fact, $R(pdX)$ acting on $\exp(ipx)$ equals $\exp(dX/dx)$ acting on $\exp(ipx)$ i.e. a photon or a particle translates by mathematically rotating with spatial frequency p.

A scalar equation may be linked to a matrix one which may have physical meaning in certain cases. We argue that mapping the wave equations of electromagnetism to a rotation in px equation equal to a translation equation makes sense and yields $\exp(ipx)$ which represents probability just as in the quantum particle case (say for an electron). Then, one may consider probabilities for various scenarios and add these to obtain an overall result in complete contrast to classical calculations.

References

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